

EFFECT OF LOW-DOSE PAX HERBAL BITTERS ON BIOCHEMICAL, INFLAMMATORY, RENAL AND HAEMATOLOGICAL INDICES IN MALE WISTAR RATS FED A HIGH-SALT DIET

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the effects of low-dose Pax Herbal Bitters on biochemical, inflammatory, renal and haematological changes associated with high salt diet-induced hypertension in male Wistar rats. For this study, 20 male albino Wistar rats with an average weight of 232 ± 1.0 g were divided into four groups. The first group was given a basal diet of rat chow, while the second was given a high salt diet. They were used as the negative and positive controls respectively. The third group was given the high salt diet along with a known anti-hypertensive drug (lisinopril), while the fourth was given the high salt diet along with a low dose (570 mg/kg) of Pax herbal bitters. The herbal bitters were administered using an oro-gastric gavage for a period of 42 days, after which the plasma haematological indices, lipid profile, kidney function, as well as the plasma levels of high sensitive C-reactive Protein (hs-CRP) were determined using standard laboratory procedures.

The results of this study revealed that the low dose Pax herbal bitters administered to the group given the high salt diet significantly ($P < 0.05$) stabilised the blood glucose level, while preventing significantly ($P < 0.05$) an increase in the plasma levels of hs-CRP, total

cholesterol, LDL-cholesterol, sodium and urea as was seen in the rats fed purely the high salt diet. It also significantly prevented ($P < 0.05$) a reduction in plasma level of HDL-cholesterol in rats fed the high salt diet and bitters when compared to the rats fed only the high salt diet.

The results of this study indicate that a low dose of Pax herbal bitters produces effects comparable to the ACE-inhibitor (lisinopril), and has the potential to prevent high salt diet induced hypertensive changes like glucose imbalance, dyslipidaemia, renal dysfunction and inflammation.

Keywords: Pax herbal bitters, hypertension, high salt diet, lisinopril, Wistar rats, hs-CRP, lipid profile, kidney function.

This manuscript is a preprint and has not undergone peer review. The findings should not be regarded as conclusive, guide clinical practice, or be reported in the media as established information.

INTRODUCTION

Background of Study

Hypertension is one of the leading causes of cardiovascular morbidity and mortality worldwide. High dietary salt intake is an established risk factor for the development of hypertension and its associated complications. Although conventional antihypertensive drugs are effective, there is growing interest in herbal preparations with potential cardioprotective properties and anti-inflammatory. Pax Herbal Bitters is a polyherbal formulation reported to possess antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties (Anionye & Onyeneke, 2015). However, limited information exists regarding its protective effects against biochemical and inflammatory alterations associated with salt-induced hypertension. Therefore, this study investigated the effects of low-dose Pax Herbal Bitters on biochemical, inflammatory, renal and haematological indices in male Wistar rats fed a high-salt diet.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study was to evaluate the protective effects of low-dose Pax Herbal Bitters against biochemical, inflammatory, renal and haematological changes associated with high salt diet-induced hypertension in male Wistar rats, and to compare its effects with those of lisinopril.

Objectives of the Research/Study

The general objective of this research was to evaluate the effect of low dose Pax herbal bitters against biochemical, inflammatory, renal and haematological changes induced by a high-salt diet in male Wistar rats

- To evaluate the effects of low-dose Pax Herbal Bitters on biochemical, inflammatory, renal and haematological changes associated with high salt diet-induced hypertension.
- To evaluate the effect of low-dose Pax Herbal Bitters on plasma lipid profile in rats fed a high-salt diet.
- To determine the effect of low-dose Pax Herbal Bitters on inflammatory markers (hs-CRP), plasma glucose concentration and renal function indices.
- To compare the effects of low-dose Pax Herbal Bitters with those of lisinopril in rats fed a high-salt diet.

History of Herbal Medicine

Bitters are traditionally alcoholic preparation flavored with botanical matter such as herbs, bark, roots, and fruit and the end result is characterized by a bitter, sour, or bittersweet flavour. They have been historically used for their medicinal and digestive properties. Most bitters contain both water and alcohol, the latter of which functions as a solvent for botanical extracts as well as a preservative.

Medicinal plants, including many now used as culinary herbs and spices, have been used as medicines for centuries in the prevention and treatment of various diseases and remain an important source of bioactive compounds with therapeutic potential (Tapsell et al., 2006). The growing interest in herbal medicine has led to increased scientific investigation of herbal preparations, including herbal bitters, for their potential roles in the prevention and management of cardiovascular and metabolic disorders.

Mechanism of Action of Bitters

A range of physiological responses occur after stimulation of the bitter receptors of the tongue. The taste of bitterness is transmitted by specific taste buds at the back of the tongue to the central nervous system; this triggers a number of reflexes that may enhance digestive secretions, appetite regulation, bile production, and gastrointestinal motility. In addition some herbal bitters have reported to possess antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties which may contribute to their therapeutic effects. (Hoffman, 1987; Bakare and Magbagbeola, 2011; Wölflle et al., 2024)

Uses of Bitters

Bitter flavored foods have a rich history in the healing arts. Consumption of bitters regularly has been shown to support digestion, stimulate appetite, promote bile secretion, and improve gastrointestinal function.

Pax Herbal Bitters

Pax Herbal Bitters is a medicine made by dissolving a drug in alcohol, made of different herbal ingredients. It promotes blood circulation, prevents kidney stones, helps in digestion, activates bile flow, increase immunity of the body against bacterial and fungal infections (Pax Herbal Clinic and Research Laboratories, 2014).

Fig. 1 Paxherbal Bitters (Pax Herbal Clinic and Research Laboratories, 2014)

Active Ingredients Glycosides, Lycopenes, Aliphatic phenols, Glycoflavones, Carotenoids, Saponins, Tannins, Quinine and Alkaloids etc. **pH value:** 4.50

Appearance Net volume of the product: 190 ml, 6.42 Fl. Oz. Characterized by dark brownish colour liquid with strong bitter taste, aromatic odour, with 100% moisture content. Readily soluble in water.

Pharmacological Properties

Pax Herbal Bitters is administered orally and contains a mixture of phytochemical constituents that may exert various biochemical and physiological effects following absorption from the gastrointestinal tract. The therapeutic activities of the preparation have been attributed to its phytochemical composition, although detailed pharmacokinetic studies on the formulation remain limited (Pax Herbal Clinic and Research Laboratories, 2014)

Reported Uses of Pax Herbal Bitters

According to Pax Herbal Clinic and Research Laboratories (2014), Pax Herbal Bitters is a herbal formulation traditionally used to support digestion, stimulate bile flow, promote blood circulation, and enhance general wellbeing. The preparation has also been reported to

possess antimicrobial and antioxidant properties, although further scientific studies are required to validate many of its claimed therapeutic effects.

Hypertension

Blood pressure is the force exerted by the blood against the walls of blood vessels, and the magnitude of this force depends on the cardiac output and the resistance of the blood vessels (Hall, 2011). Hypertension, also known as high blood pressure (HBP), is a long-term medical condition in which the blood pressure in the arteries is persistently elevated higher than 140 over 90 mmHg (millimeters of mercury) (Naish and Syndercombe Court, 2014). A diagnosis of hypertension may be made when one or both readings are high: systolic (the pressure as the heart pumps blood around the body), given first; or diastolic (pressure as the heart relaxes and refills with blood), given second (Naish and Syndercombe Court, 2014).

High blood pressure usually do not cause symptoms. Long term high blood pressure, however, is a major risk factor for coronary artery disease, stroke, heart failure, peripheral vascular disease, vision loss, and chronic kidney disease (Nwankwo et al., 2013).

Types of Hypertension

High blood pressure is classified as either primary (essential) high blood pressure or secondary high blood pressure.

Primary hypertension accounts for approximately 90–95% of cases and are due to nonspecific lifestyle and genetic and environmental factors. Lifestyle factors such as excess salt intake, obesity, smoking, and alcohol consumption etc.

Secondary hypertension accounts for the remaining 5–10% of cases and results from identifiable causes, such as chronic kidney disease, renal artery stenosis, endocrine disorder, and use of certain medication like oral contraceptives (Poulter et al., 2015).

Hypertension is a major risk factor for cardiovascular disease, stroke, heart failure, and chronic kidney disease. Persistent elevation of blood pressure can lead to progressive damage of target organs and increased morbidity and mortality (Nwankwo et al., 2013).

Pathophysiology of Hypertension

Hypertension results from a complex interaction of genes and environmental factors (Ehret et al., 2011). Blood pressure can also rise with aging and the risk of becoming hypertensive in later life is considerable (Vasan et al., 2002). Several environmental factors influence blood pressure. High salt intake raises the blood pressure in salt sensitive individuals (Meng et al., 2012). Lack of exercise, obesity, depression, caffeine consumption

(Mesas et al., 2011), and vitamin D deficiency can also be a causative factor even though their role is not yet fully understood (Vaidya and Forman, 2010).

Diagnosis of hypertension is made by measuring blood pressure over a number of clinic visits, using a sphygmomanometer.

Some Medications Are Used to Treat Hypertension

Thiazide diuretics Diuretics, sometimes called water pills, are medications that act on your kidneys to help your body eliminate sodium and water, reducing blood volume (Longo et al., 2012).

Beta blockers These medications reduce the workload on your heart and open your blood vessels, causing your heart to beat slower and with less force. Beta blockers include acebutolol (Sectral), atenolol (Tenormin) and others (James et al., 2014).

Angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors These medications — such as lisinopril (Zestril), benazepril (Lotensin), captopril (Capoten) and others — help relax blood vessels by blocking the formation of a natural chemical that narrows blood vessels (Ogbru, 2010).

Lisinopril

Fig. 2 Structure of lisinopril

Lisinopril is a drug of the angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor class used primarily in treatment of high blood pressure, heart failure, and after heart attacks. It is also used for preventing kidney and eye complications in people with diabetes. Lisinopril is typically used for the treatment of hypertension, congestive heart failure, acute myocardial infarction, and diabetic nephropathy (Patchett et al., 1980).

Mechanism of action Lisinopril is an ACE Inhibitor, meaning it blocks the actions of angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) in the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS), keeping Angiotensin I from being converted to Angiotensin II. The inhibition of this system causes an overall decrease in blood pressure (Katzung and Bertram, 2012).

Usual Adult Dose for Hypertension: Initial dose: 10 mg orally once a day; 5 mg orally once a day. Maintenance dose: 20 to 40 mg orally once a day. Maximum dose: 80 mg orally once a day.

Calcium Channel Blockers These medications — including amlodipine (Norvasc), diltiazem (Cardizem, Tiazac, others) and others — help relax the muscles of your blood vessels. Some slow your heart rate (Nelson, 2010).

High Salt Diet and Hypertension

The ancient Chinese (2000 years BC) reported that “salt hardens the pulse,” implying that there is a relationship between salt intake, arterial pressure, and vascular stiffness (Ruskin, 1956). However, a lot of research was carried out in the 20th century resulting in epidemiological, interventional, and experimental reports. In one of the earliest epidemiological studies a direct relationship between the prevalence of hypertension and daily salt intake among individuals was reported. The more recent study shows the direct relationship between the prevalence of hypertension within a specific population (Cook et al., 2007).

Further, early experimental work was performed on rats fed diets consisting of different amounts of salt showed that as the average daily salt intake increased, so did arterial pressure (Ball et al., 1957). Later, selective inbreeding techniques performed by Dahl and Heine developed 2 genetically different strains of rats that were either salt-sensitive or resistant to the blood pressure increasing effects of high salt intake (Dahl, 1961).

Salt Induced Hypertension in Albino Rats

High sodium intake has been implicated in the development of hypertension in both animals and man (Meneely et al., 1953) and has been reported to accelerate spontaneous hypertension in rats (Dahl, 1961). In a previous study, it was demonstrated that long-term (7 months) high sodium intake aggravated the hypertension of Spontaneously Hypertensive Rats by elevating peripheral vascular resistance. A similar response to sodium was reported by Tobian, Ganguli, and Dahl (Tobian et al., 1974) for the salt-sensitive rat of the Dahl strain, whereas the resistant control strain of rats responded with vasodilation, increased cardiac output, and no change in blood pressure.

Inflammation

Inflammation (from Latin *inflammatio*) is part of the complex biological response of body tissues to harmful stimuli, such as pathogens, damaged cells, or irritants, and is a protective response involving immune cells, blood vessels, and molecular mediators (Ferrero-Miliani et al., 2007). The function of inflammation is to eliminate the initial cause of cell

injury, clear out necrotic cells and tissues damaged from the original insult and the inflammatory process, and to initiate tissue repair. The classical signs of inflammation are heat, pain, redness, swelling, and loss of function. Inflammation is a generic response, and therefore it is considered as a mechanism of innate immunity. Too little inflammation could lead to progressive tissue destruction by the harmful stimulus (e.g. bacteria) and compromise the survival of the organism. In contrast, chronic inflammation may lead to a host of diseases, such as hay fever, atherosclerosis, and even cancer (e.g. gallbladder carcinoma). Inflammation is therefore normally closely regulated by the body (Abbas et., 2009).

Types of Inflammation

Inflammation can be classified as either acute or chronic. Acute inflammation is the initial response of the body to harmful stimuli and is achieved by the increased movement of plasma and leukocytes (especially granulocytes) from the blood into the injured tissues. Chronic inflammation is a prolonged response that leads to a progressive shift in the type of cells present at the site of inflammation, such as mononuclear cells, and is characterized by simultaneous destruction and healing of the tissue from the inflammatory process (Hall, 2011).

Mechanism of Inflammation

Inflammation involves a coordinated vascular and cellular response. Following tissue injury or exposure to inflammatory stimuli, mediators such as histamine, prostaglandins, cytokines, and nitric oxide are released, causing vasodilation and increased vascular permeability. These changes promote the migration of immune cells and plasma proteins into affected tissues, resulting in the characteristic signs of inflammation, including redness, heat, swelling, and pain (Kumar et al., 2004).

Inflammatory Markers

Inflammatory markers are substances measured in blood to assess the presence and severity of inflammation. Common markers include erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), C-reactive protein (CRP) and plasma viscosity (PV). Among these, CRP is considered one of the most sensitive markers because it responds rapidly to inflammatory changes and is less affected by external factors than ESR or PV (Aguar et al., 2013).

Inflammation in Hypertension

Increasing evidence suggests that inflammation contributes to the development and progression of hypertension. Elevated levels of inflammatory markers, particularly CRP and

interleukin-6 (IL-6), have been associated with increased blood pressure and cardiovascular risk (Sung et al., 2003). Experimental studies in salt-sensitive hypertensive rats have demonstrated infiltration of immune cells into the kidneys and vascular tissues, suggesting that inflammation may contribute to both the initiation and maintenance of hypertension (Heijnen et al., 2004; Rodriguez-Iturbe et al., 2004). Chronic inflammation has also been linked to vascular stiffness and endothelial dysfunction, both of which promote elevated blood pressure (Mahmud et al., 2005).

Atherosclerosis

Atherosclerosis is now recognized as a chronic inflammatory disease of the arterial wall. Inflammatory processes contribute to plaque formation, progression, and rupture, leading to cardiovascular complications such as myocardial infarction and stroke. Elevated inflammatory markers, particularly CRP, have been associated with increased risk of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (Libby, 2002).

C-reactive Protein (CRP)

C-reactive protein (CRP) is an acute-phase protein synthesized primarily by the liver in response to inflammation. CRP concentrations increase during infection, tissue injury, and inflammatory diseases, making it a widely used biomarker of systemic inflammation. Elevated CRP levels have also been associated with hypertension, atherosclerosis, and increased cardiovascular risk. High-sensitivity CRP (hs-CRP) assays allow detection of low-grade inflammation and may be useful in predicting future cardiovascular events (Libby and Ridker, 1999; Liuzzo et al., 1994).

Angiotensin Converting Enzyme (ACE)

Angiotensin-converting enzyme, or ACE, is a central component of the renin-angiotensin system (RAS), which controls blood pressure by regulating the volume of fluids in the body. It converts the hormone angiotensin I to the active vasoconstrictor angiotensin II. Therefore, ACE indirectly increases blood pressure by causing blood vessels to constrict. ACE inhibitors are widely used as pharmaceutical drugs for treatment of cardiovascular diseases. It is located mainly in the capillaries of the lungs but can also be found in endothelial and kidney epithelial cells (Skeggs et al., 1956).

Mechanism of action ACE is a zinc metalloenzyme (Wang et al., 2016). The zinc ion is essential to its activity, since it directly participates in the catalysis of the peptide hydrolysis. Therefore, ACE can be inhibited by metal-chelating agents (Bunning and Riordan, 1985). The

E384 residue was found to have a dual function. First it acts as a general base to activate water as a nucleophile. Then it acts as a general acid to cleave the C-N bond. The function of the chloride ion is very complex and is highly debated. The anion activation by chloride is a characteristic feature of ACE (Zhang et al., 2013). It was experimentally determined that the activation of hydrolysis by chloride is highly dependent on the substrate. While it increases hydrolysis rates for e.g. Hip-His-Leu it inhibits hydrolysis of other substrates like Hip-Ala-Pro. Under physiological conditions the enzyme reaches about 60% of its maximal activity toward angiotensin I while it reaches its full activity toward bradykinin. It is therefore assumed that the function of the anion activation in ACE provides high substrate (Bunning, 1985).

ACE Inhibitors ACE inhibitors are widely used as pharmaceutical drugs in the treatment of conditions such as high blood pressure, heart failure. ACE inhibitors inhibit ACE competitively. That results in the decreased formation of angiotensin II and decreased metabolism of bradykinin, which leads to systematic dilation of the arteries and veins and a decrease in arterial blood pressure. These medicines also increase the release of water and sodium to the urine, which also lowers blood pressure. ACE inhibitors can be used alone or in combination with a diuretic or other medicine (Klabunde, 2009).

Haematology and Haematological Indices

Hematology is the branch of medicine that is concerned with the study, diagnosis, treatment and prevention of diseases related to blood. Hematology also includes the study of etiology. It involves treating diseases that affect the production of blood and its components such as blood cells, hemoglobin, blood proteins, bone marrow, platelets, blood vessels, spleen and mechanism of coagulation.

There are various people that are affected by hematology. A few of those different types of blood conditions that are looked at include anemia, hemophilia, general blood clots, bleeding disorders etc. Hematological indices include hemoglobin count, packed cell volume (PCV) or hematocrit, red blood cell count, mean cell volume (MCV), total blood volume, plasma volume, white blood cell count, neutrophils, lymphocytes, eosinophils, basophils, monocytes and so on.

Hematological Reference Values

- Hemoglobin – (male) 13.5-18.0 g/dl (female) 11.5-16.0 g/dl
- Packed cell volume – (male) 0.40-0.54 l/l (female) 0.37–0.47 l/l
- Red blood cell count – (male) $4.5\text{--}6.5 \times 10^{12}/\text{l}$ (female) $3.9\text{--}5.6 \times 10^{12}/\text{l}$

- Mean cell volume – 81-100 fl
- Mean cell hemoglobin – 27–32 pg
- White blood cell count – $4.0-11.0 \times 10^9/l$

Hematological Indices and Hypertension

A study was carried out with the aim of evaluating the hematological changes in primary hypertension, and a total of 100 patients diagnosed for primary hypertension and 100 normotensive subjects were used. The result was thus: It was observed that the mean values of Hemoglobin, Erythrocyte count, Hematocrit, MCH and MCHC were increased in primary hypertension while the mean levels of MCV were found to be lower in the hypertensive group when compared to normotensive subjects. Conclusion: Hypertension has impact on hematocrit, hemoglobin, RBC count, WBC count and Platelet count which can be used for early detection of hypertensive prone individuals (Ranjith-Babu et al., 2015).

Assessment of Blood Glucose Level

Blood glucose is the concentration of glucose (sugar) present in the blood of a human or animal and is the primary source of energy for the body's cells. Glucose homeostasis is tightly regulated by hormones, particularly insulin, which facilitates the uptake and utilization of glucose by tissues (Young, 1977). Abnormal blood glucose levels may indicate metabolic dysfunction, with persistent elevation resulting in hyperglycaemia and diabetes mellitus (Walker and Rodgers, 2006).

Assessment of blood glucose is widely used in experimental and clinical studies to evaluate metabolic status and the effects of dietary, pharmacological, or pathological interventions. Since some herbal preparations may influence carbohydrate metabolism and insulin activity, measurement of blood glucose provides an important indicator of the metabolic effects of therapeutic agents (Pagana, 2014).

Hypertension and Blood Glucose

High blood pressure (hypertension) can lead to many complications of diabetes, including diabetic eye disease and kidney disease, or make them worse. Most people with

diabetes will eventually have high blood pressure, along with other heart and circulation problems.

Diabetes damages arteries and makes them targets for hardening, called atherosclerosis. That can cause high blood pressure, which if not treated, can lead to trouble including blood vessel damage, heart attack, and kidney failure (Dansinger, 2017). Hypertension in insulin resistance states is generally attributed to hyperinsulinemia, with resulting increases in renal sodium retention and/or sympathetic nervous system activity. However, recent data from our laboratory suggest that cellular insulin resistance, rather than hyperinsulinemia per se, may lead to hypertension. The basic tenet proposed in this review is that the common mechanism involved in the development of hypertension in both type I and type II diabetes mellitus is a deficiency of insulin at the cellular level. Recent observations suggest that impaired cellular response to insulin predisposes to increased vascular smooth muscle (VSM) tone (the hallmark of hypertension in the diabetic state). For example, recently reported studies demonstrates that insulin in physiological doses attenuates the vascular contractile response to phenylephrine, serotonin, and potassium chloride. Thus, insulin appears to normally modulate (attenuate) VSM contractile responses to vasoactive factors, and insulin resistance should accordingly be associated with enhanced vascular reactivity. Abnormal VSM cell calcium $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ homeostasis may be the nexus between insulin resistance and increased VSM tone (Sowers et al., 1991).

Dyslipidaemia and Hypertension

Lipids are large and diverse group of naturally occurring organic compounds that are related by their solubility in non-polar organic solvents and generally not soluble in water.

Classes of lipid include naturally occurring fatty acids, cholesterol, triacylglycerol, lipoprotein etc. (Ruesch, 2013).

Classification of Lipid Concentrations

Lipids are transported in the blood as lipoproteins because they are insoluble in water. The major lipid components commonly assessed are total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), and very low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (VLDL-C) (Dargel, 1989)

Total Cholesterol

Total cholesterol (TC) is an important indicator of cardiovascular health. According to the National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP), a total cholesterol level below 200 mg/dL is considered desirable, while levels above 240 mg/dL are regarded as high. Elevated cholesterol levels are associated with increased risk of cardiovascular disease. Cholesterol also serves as a precursor for steroid hormones, bile acids, and vitamin D (Ahmed et al., 1998; Hanukoglu, 1992).

Triglycerides

Triglycerides are fats transported mainly by VLDL in the bloodstream and serve as an important energy reserve. Normal triglyceride levels are below 150 mg/dL, while elevated levels are associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease (Ginsberg and Goldberg, 2001).

LDL Cholesterol

Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol is commonly referred to as "bad cholesterol" because elevated levels contribute to plaque formation within arterial walls. LDL levels below 100 mg/dL are considered optimal, while high levels are associated with increased cardiovascular risk (Ginsberg and Goldberg, 2001).

HDL Cholesterol

High-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol is known as "good cholesterol" because it transports excess cholesterol from peripheral tissues back to the liver for metabolism. Higher HDL levels are associated with reduced cardiovascular risk, whereas levels below 40 mg/dL are considered a risk factor for cardiovascular disease (Ridker et al., 2010).

VLDL Cholesterol

Very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) transports triglycerides and cholesterol from the liver to peripheral tissues. Elevated VLDL levels have been associated with atherosclerosis and cardiovascular disease (Sundaram et al., 2010).

Lipid Profile and Hypertension

Lipids are transported in the circulation as lipoproteins and originate from both endogenous synthesis in the liver and exogenous dietary sources. Abnormal lipid metabolism results in hyperlipidemia, a condition characterized by elevated blood lipid levels. Increased

levels of total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, and triglycerides contribute to the development of atherosclerosis through plaque formation within arterial walls, leading to narrowing and stiffening of blood vessels. Conversely, HDL cholesterol exerts a protective effect by facilitating reverse cholesterol transport. Several studies have demonstrated a strong association between dyslipidemia, hypertension, and cardiovascular disease (Kumar et al., 2004; Grundy and Vega, 1998; Mora et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2013).

Renal Dysfunction in Hypertension

There are two kidneys on either side of the spine that are each approximately the size of a human fist. They're located posterior to the abdomen and below the rib cage. Kidneys play several vital roles in maintaining health. One of their most important jobs is to filter waste materials from the blood and expel them from the body as urine. The kidneys also help control the levels of water and various essential minerals in the body. In addition, they're critical to the production of:

- vitamin D
- red blood cells
- hormones that regulate blood pressure

If there is a suspected problem with the kidneys a kidney function test is required. These are simple blood and urine tests that can identify problems with the kidneys. Kidney function testing is also done if other conditions that can harm the kidneys, such as diabetes or high blood pressure are present. They can help doctors monitor these conditions (Stang, 2015).

Causes of Kidney Disease

The major causes of kidney disease include diabetes mellitus and hypertension, which are the leading causes of end-stage renal disease (ESRD). Other causes include glomerulonephritis, infections, kidney stones, inherited disorders such as polycystic kidney disease, and prolonged use of certain medications or illicit drugs. Early diagnosis and appropriate treatment can help prevent or slow the progression of kidney disease (National Kidney Foundation, 2015).

Kidney Function and Hypertension

Your kidneys and your circulatory system depend on each other for good health. Over time, high blood pressure harms renal blood vessels. The nephrons in the kidneys are supplied with a dense network of blood vessels, and high volumes of blood flow through them. Over time, uncontrolled high blood pressure can cause arteries around the kidneys to

narrow, weaken or harden. These damaged arteries are not able to deliver enough blood to the kidney tissue.

- Damaged kidney arteries do not filter blood well. Kidneys have small, finger-like nephrons that filter your blood. Each nephron receives its blood supply through tiny hair-like capillaries, the smallest of all blood vessels. When the arteries become damaged, the nephrons do not receive the essential oxygen and nutrients — and the kidneys lose their ability to filter blood and regulate the fluid, hormones, acids and salts in the body.

- Damaged kidneys fail to regulate blood pressure. Healthy kidneys produce a hormone called aldosterone to help the body regulate blood pressure. Kidney damage and uncontrolled high blood pressure each contribute to a negative spiral. As more arteries become blocked and stop functioning, the kidneys eventually fail (American Heart Association, 2016).

Kidney Function Test

To check kidney function, the doctor orders a set of tests that can estimate glomerular filtration rate (GFR). GFR tells the doctor how quickly the kidneys are clearing waste from the body. Some of these tests are:

- Urinalysis
- Serum Creatinine Test
- Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN)
- Urine Tests (urinalysis, urine protein, microalbuminuria, creatine clearance)

(Stang, 2015).

Depending on the underlying cause, some types of kidney disease can be treated. Often, though, chronic kidney disease has no cure. Treatment usually consists of measures to help control signs and symptoms, reduce complications, and slow progression of the disease. If your kidneys become severely damaged, you may need treatment for end-stage kidney disease.

Treating the cause: The doctors work to slow or control the cause of the kidney disease. Treatment options vary, depending on the cause.

Treating complications: Kidney disease complications can be controlled to make the patient more comfortable. Treatments may include:

- High blood pressure medications
- Medications to lower cholesterol levels

- Medications to treat anemia
- Medications to relieve swelling
- Medications to protect your bones
- A lower protein diet to minimize waste products in your blood.

Treatment for end-stage kidney disease

- Dialysis
- Kidney transplant (Tidy, 2014).

Determination of Plasma Sodium (Na⁺) and Potassium (K⁺)

Potassium (K) is the major cation found inside of cells. The proper level of potassium is essential for normal cell function. An abnormal increase of potassium (hyperkalemia) or decrease of potassium (hypokalemia) can profoundly affect the nervous system and heart, and when extreme, can be fatal. The normal blood potassium level is 3.5 - 5.0 millimoles/liter (mmol/l). Sodium (Na) is the major extracellular cation and it plays a role in body fluid distribution. Concentration of sodium ions inside the plasma (extracellular) is 130-145 mmol/l. Higher and lower concentrations are referred to as hypernatremia and hyponatremia, respectively (Marshall and Bangert, 1995).

Determination of Plasma Urea

Urea is the principal nitrogenous waste product of metabolism and is generated from protein breakdown. It is eliminated from the body mostly by the kidneys in urine, and its concentration can be measured, first in urine and later in blood. The rate of urea production is influenced by protein content of diet; low-protein diet is associated with reduced urea production and high-protein diet is associated with increased urea production. Starvation is also associated with increased urea production as a result of increased protein released from muscle tissue breakdown that occurs during starvation as a source of energy (Watford, 2013). Most of the urea produced in the liver is transported in blood to the kidneys where it is eliminated from the body in urine (Weiner et al., 2015). Urea analysis can be expressed in two different ways; Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN) which is measured in mg/dL and Urea measured in mmol/L. The reference (normal) range: serum/plasma urea 2.5- 7.8 mmol/L, serum/plasma BUN 7.0 – 22 mg/dL.

Causes of increased serum/plasma Urea: Increased plasma/serum urea can either be caused by increased urea production or decreased elimination of urea (or combination of both). Most often it is decrease elimination of urea which can most likely be as a result of advanced renal

failure with consequent reduction in glomerular filtration rate. Other non renal causes of increased plasma/serum urea are; Increased dietary protein and ageing, gastrointestinal hemorrhage associated with protein intake (Witting et al., 2006). Conditions that are associated with tissue damage e.g. Trauma, surgery, starvation this will cause increased protein catabolism and consequent increase in urea synthesis, low circulatory states like heart failure, dehydration (Aronson et al., 2004). Drugs like corticosteroids that induce catabolism with increased protein break down and increased Urea production. Also it is important to note that reduced plasma/serum Urea is also clinically significant although not very common and some of the causes are low protein diet, pregnancy and advanced liver disease (Kalhan, 2000). Plasma/serum Urea test of renal function has been discovered to be less sensitive and specific, urea creatine measurement is more specific (Baum et al., 1975).

Determination of Plasma Creatinine

Creatinine is a waste product excreted from the blood into the urine via the kidney. Kidney damage results in creatinine being retained in the blood. Creatinine is a chemical waste product of creatine. Creatine is a chemical made by the body and is used to supply energy mainly to muscles. This test is done to see how well your kidneys work. Creatinine is removed from the body entirely by the kidneys. If kidney function is not normal, the creatinine level in your blood will increase. This is because less creatinine is released through your urine (Inker et al., 2015). Creatinine clearance in the kidney gives a measure of the Glomerular Filtration Rate (GFR) and is the standard marker for renal function. Since its rate of excretion is constant, elevation of plasma creatinine is indicative of under-excretion, suggesting kidney impairment. Elevated levels are associated with acute and chronic renal insufficiency and urinary tract obstruction. Levels below 0.6 mg/dL are of no significance. A normal result is 0.7 to 1.3 mg/dL for men and 0.6 to 1.1 mg/dL for women. Women usually have a lower creatinine level than men. This is because women usually have less muscle mass than men. Creatinine level varies based on a person's size and muscle mass. The examples above are common measurements for results of these tests. Normal value ranges may vary slightly among different laboratories (Landry and Bazari, 2011).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Test Materials

Pax herbal bitters was purchased from a licensed pharmaceutical outlet in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. The product was obtained in liquid form and stored at room temperature (25°C) throughout the experimental period. Distilled water was also purchased from the Department of Chemistry, University of Benin, Benin City. Randox kits for Total cholesterol, HDL-cholesterol, triglyceride, glucose, Urea and Creatinine were all obtained from Randox Laboratories UK, through the manufacturer's Nigeria representative. Rat high sensitive C-Reactive Protein (hs-CRP) ELISA kit was also obtained.

Apparatus and Equipment

The apparatus used for this study included an analytical weighing balance, water distiller, HH-W constant temperature water bath, refrigerator, 80-2 model electric centrifuge, T70 UV/VIS spectrophotometer, flame photometer, Sysmex KX-21N Automated Haematology Analyser, automated micropipettes, animal cages, oro-gastric gavage, and standard laboratory glassware.

Experimental Animals

All the experimental animals for this study were handled in compliance with the international guidelines prescribed (CCAC, 1984). Twenty (20) male albino Wistar rats were obtained from a licensed laboratory animal breeding facility in Osun State, Nigeria. The rats were housed in a well-ventilated room, in plastic cages with wire-mesh on the floor and top, in the animal house of the Department of Medical Biochemistry, School of Basic Medical Sciences, University of Benin, Benin City, Nigeria. The temperature of their environment ranged between 25-30°C and they were allowed the recommended diurnal 12-hr light and dark cycle. The rats were fed ad-libitum with a modified standard pelleted grower's mash and clean tap water for two weeks to allow acclimatization.

Design of the Experimental Diets

The control or basal diet was a modified standard pelleted grower's mash that was designed/formulated following the suggestions of Nevela et al. (2000) and Cho et al. (2000). The high salt diet (hypertension-inducing diet) was prepared by adding a proportionate

quantity of the basal diet with 8% NaCl (to make the diet high in salt for the purpose of making the rats hypertensive) (Ayala et al., 2007).

The final composition of both the basal and experimental diets was as indicated in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1: Composition of the basal diet (g/1000g) based on a slight modification (as proposed by Nevela et al., 2000 and Cho et al., 2000) of the standard pelleted growers mash of Jerrison Agro Allied Services, Benin City, Nigeria.

Ingredients	Basal Diet (g)
Bone Meal	10.0
Wheat Offal	300.0
Palm Kernel Cake	232.0
Groundnut Cake	128.0
Fish Meal (65%)	12.0
Grower Premix	2.4
Maize	260.0
Limestone	52.0
Lysine	1.6
Salt	2.0

Table 2: Composition of the high-salt diet (g/1000g) (hypertension-inducing diet) based on the adaptation of the methods of Reeves et al. (1993), Soliman et al. (2012) and Ajayi et al. (2012).

Ingredients	High-salt Diet (g)
Basal Diet in Table 3.1	920.0
Pure analytical grade NaCl	80.0
Total	1000.0

Experimental Design

Twenty (20) male albino rats of the Wistar strain weighing between 200-300 g (average 232 g) were used for this study. After 14 days acclimatization, the 20 animals were weighed and divided into four (4) groups of five (5) rats each, ensuring that the weights of the

rats in a group were of equal weight range, such that the average weight of all the groups at the beginning of the experimental period was around 232 g. The rats were fed ad-libitum during the entire course of the 6-weeks (42 days) study, according to the feeding protocol assigned for each group. They were allowed the recommended 12-hr light and dark cycle. The quantity of feed consumed daily was carefully determined. The rats were housed in plastic cages with wire-mesh flooring allowing the rat-excreta to be collected into another steel tray receptacle below lined with a bedding material to prevent coprophagy. The cages, their surroundings, the receptacle tray below with its bedding, were cleaned and disinfected daily. The animals were given orally, the herbal bitters and drug using an oro-gastric gavage, according to the equivalent dose (to the weight of the rats) of the effective dose already prescribed for man. An equivalent volume of distilled water was given to the control groups (1 and 2). The animals were then observed for signs of toxicity and mortality.

Feeding Protocol

Control groups:

- Group 1: Basal diet for 6 weeks + distilled water (-ve control)
- Group 2: High salt diet for 6 weeks + distilled water (+ve control)

Experimental groups:

- Group 3: High salt diet + ACE-inhibitor (lisinopril – 0.14 mg/kg rat body weight) for 6 weeks
- Group 4: High salt diet + Pax herbal bitters (low dose – 570 mg/kg body weight of rats) for 6 weeks.

Dosage Regimen for Pax Herbal Bitters

The manufacturer's recommendation and prior studies have established an effective low dose for the herbal bitters for an adult man to be an average 40 ml daily as a single dose (Mendie, 2009; Anionye et al., 2015, 2017). Appropriate calculations were carried out to determine the initial equivalent doses of the bitters in ml/g mean body weight of the rats. As the initial mean weights of rats in each group at the beginning of the study was about 232 g, the equivalent volume of the bitters/distilled water that will be given to the rats was calculated as 0.133 ml (approximately 0.13 ml) which corresponds to a dose of 570 mg/kg of rat body weight.

Dosage Regimen for Lisinopril

Following the same principles as adopted for the dosage of the herbal bitters, the equivalent dose was calculated as 0.14 mg/kg of rat body weight. The drug was formulated by dissolving 0.041 mg of Lisinopril in distilled water and making it up to 1 ml which was given daily to the rats in the assigned group using an oro-gastric gavage.

Determination of Body Weight

The body weight of each rat was assessed using a sensitive balance during the acclimatization period. The rats were weighed once before commencement of dosing (day 1), once weekly during the dosing period (day 7, 14, 21, 28, 35) and once on the day of sacrifice (day 42) (Aniagu et al., 2005). Body weight measurements were used to adjust treatment doses, calculate weekly weight gain, and determine food efficiency.

Determination of Feed Intake

The quantity of feed given to each group of rats daily was determined by subtracting the quantity of feed left the next morning from that given the previous day. From the results the average quantity of feed consumed weekly by the rats was determined using a sensitive balance from the commencement of dosing (day 1), until the day of sacrifice (day 42) (Aniagu et al., 2005). The results were used along with the weight gain of the rats to determine their food efficiency.

Food Efficiency

This is determined using the formula: $\text{Food efficiency} = (\text{Weight gain/day/rat}) \times 100 / (\text{Feed Consumed/day/rat})$ (Matos et al., 2005)

Relative Organ Weight

At the end of the 42-day experimental period, just after the rats were weighed, sacrificed (using chloroform anaesthesia), blood samples were collected from them, different organs namely the heart, liver, kidneys and the aorta of the respective rats from all groups was carefully dissected out and weighed in grams (this weight was designated as the absolute organ weight). The relative organ weight was then calculated using the formula below:

$\text{Relative Organ Weight} = (\text{Absolute organ weight (g)} \times 100) / \text{Body weight of rat on sacrifice day (g)}$ (Aniagu et al., 2005).

Blood Sample Collection and Preparation

Two specimen bottles were used for collection of blood from each animal. Anticoagulant bottles containing lithium heparin and K₂EDTA for assay of biochemical parameters and haematological tests were used. The last dose of the respective diets, drugs and bitters was administered on the morning of the 42nd day. All meals were stopped by 7 pm on the 42nd day. After an overnight fast, blood samples were collected following chloroform anaesthesia in accordance with laboratory procedures, using syringes and needles via the inferior vena cava and cardiac puncture, and put into already labeled K₂EDTA and lithium heparin bottles. The samples were then mixed by gentle inversion. The samples in the K₂EDTA anticoagulant bottles were sent for automated analysis for full/complete blood count. The samples in the lithium heparin bottles were centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 mins to obtain plasma. The plasma supernatants were separated into sterile plain bottles and were used for assay of the required biochemical indices. Where immediate analysis was not possible, the samples were stored in the refrigerator at 2-8°C and analysis carried out within 4 days.

Measurement of Some Biochemical Indices Associated with Hypertension

Markers of Inflammation

High Sensitive C-Reactive Protein (hs-CRP)

The rat high sensitivity C-Reactive Protein ELISA Kit was used (MyBioSource, 2014a). This test uses the double antibody sandwich ELISA technique. This CRP-HS ELISA kit is a 1.5 hour solid-phase ELISA designed for the quantitative determination of Rat CRP-HS.

Principle of the Assay

The assay is based on the sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) technique. Microplate wells pre-coated with monoclonal antibodies specific for rat hs-CRP bind the protein present in standards and samples. Following the addition of enzyme-conjugated antibodies and substrate solution, a colour reaction develops in proportion to the concentration of hs-CRP present in the sample. The absorbance was measured at 450 nm using a microplate reader, and hs-CRP concentrations were determined from a standard curve.

Procedure

Fifty microlitres (50 μ L) of standards and samples were added into appropriately labelled wells of the antibody-coated microplate. One hundred microlitres (100 μ L) of conjugate reagent was added and the plate was incubated at 37°C for 1 hour. The wells were washed five times to remove unbound materials. Subsequently, 50 μ L each of substrate A and substrate B were added and incubated at 37°C for 10–15 minutes. The reaction was terminated by adding 50 μ L of stop solution to each well. Absorbance was read immediately at 450 nm using a microplate reader.

Calculation

A standard curve was prepared using the absorbance values of the standards. The concentration of hs-CRP in each sample was obtained by interpolation from the standard curve.

Haematological Assays: Full/Complete Blood Count

Full blood count parameters were analysed using a Sysmex KX-21N automated haematology analyser according to the manufacturer's instructions (Sysmex, 2003). The analyser operates using the electrical impedance principle for cell counting and a non-cyanide haemoglobin method for haemoglobin determination (Sysmex, 2003).

Parameters determined included haemoglobin concentration (Hb), packed cell volume (PCV), red blood cell count (RBC), white blood cell count (WBC), platelet count, mean cell volume (MCV), mean cell haemoglobin (MCH), and mean cell haemoglobin concentration (MCHC).

Assessment of Blood Glucose Level

Plasma glucose concentration was determined using Randox diagnostic kits (Randox Laboratories Ltd., United Kingdom).

Principle

The assay is based on the glucose oxidase method described by Barham and Trinder (1972). Glucose present in the sample is oxidised by glucose oxidase to produce gluconic acid and hydrogen peroxide. In the presence of peroxidase, hydrogen peroxide reacts with phenol and 4-aminophenazone to form a red-violet quinoneimine dye. The intensity of the

colour produced is directly proportional to the glucose concentration and is measured spectrophotometrically at 500 nm.

Procedure The following were pipetted into separate clean dry test tubes labelled as blank, standard and test:

Addition sequence	Blank (ml)	Standard (ml)	Test (ml)
Glucose Reagent (L1)	1.0	1.0	1.0
Distilled water	0.01	-	-
Glucose Standard	-	0.01	-
Sample	-	-	0.01

The samples were properly mixed and incubated at 37°C for 10 min. The absorbance of the Standard and Test samples was then measured against the blank at wavelength of 500 nm.

Calculation

$$\text{Total glucose in mg/dl} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of Test sample}}{\text{Absorbance of Standard sample}} \times 100$$

Results Healthy Wistar albino rats have fasting blood glucose values between 80-110 mg/dl.

Assessment of Lipid Profile

Determination of Plasma Total Cholesterol (Trinder, 1969)

Plasma total cholesterol was determined using Randox diagnostic kits based on the enzymatic CHOD-PAP method described by Trinder (1969). Cholesterol is enzymatically hydrolysed and oxidised, producing hydrogen peroxide which reacts with phenol and 4-aminoantipyrine to form a coloured quinoneimine compound measured spectrophotometrically.

Determination of Plasma HDL-Cholesterol (Trinder, 1969; Tietz, 1990)

Plasma HDL-cholesterol was determined using the precipitation method described by Tietz (1990). Low-density lipoproteins (LDL), very low-density lipoproteins (VLDL), and chylomicrons were precipitated using phosphotungstic acid and magnesium ions. The

cholesterol concentration remaining in the HDL-containing supernatant was subsequently determined enzymatically.

Determination of Plasma Triglycerides (Trinder, 1969; Tietz, 1990)

Plasma triglyceride concentration was determined enzymatically using Randox diagnostic kits according to the method described by Tietz (1990). Triglycerides were hydrolysed by lipase to produce glycerol, which was subsequently oxidised to generate hydrogen peroxide. The resulting coloured complex was measured spectrophotometrically.

Determination of Plasma LDL-Cholesterol (Trinder, 1969; Tietz, 1990)

Plasma LDL-cholesterol concentration was calculated using the Friedewald equation (Friedewald et al., 1972):

$$\text{LDL-Cholesterol (mmol/L)} = \text{Total Cholesterol} - \text{HDL-Cholesterol} - (\text{Triglycerides} \div 2.2)$$

For values expressed in mg/dL:

$$\text{LDL-Cholesterol (mg/dL)} = \text{Total Cholesterol} - \text{HDL-Cholesterol} - (\text{Triglycerides} \div 5)$$

Determination of Plasma VLDL-Cholesterol

Plasma VLDL-cholesterol concentration was estimated using the Friedewald equation (Friedewald et al., 1972):

$$\text{VLDL-Cholesterol (mmol/L)} = \text{Triglycerides} \div 2.2$$

For values expressed in mg/dL:

$$\text{VLDL-Cholesterol (mg/dL)} = \text{Triglycerides} \div 5$$

Assessment of Kidney Function Status

Determination of Plasma Sodium (Na⁺) and Potassium (K⁺)

Plasma sodium and potassium concentrations were determined using a flame photometer according to the method of Kanagasabapathy and Kumari (2000). The method is based on the emission of characteristic wavelengths of light by sodium and potassium ions when introduced into a flame. The intensity of emitted light is proportional to the concentration of the respective ions in the sample.

Determination of Plasma Urea

Plasma urea concentration was determined using Randox diagnostic kits based on the urease-Berthelot reaction described by Weatherburn (1967). Urea is hydrolysed by urease to produce ammonia, which subsequently reacts to form a coloured complex measured spectrophotometrically. The intensity of the colour produced is directly proportional to the concentration of urea present in the sample.

Determination of Plasma Creatinine

Plasma creatinine concentration was determined using Randox diagnostic kits based on the Jaffe reaction as described by Bartels and Bohmer (1972). In alkaline solution, creatinine reacts with picric acid to form a coloured complex whose intensity is proportional to the concentration of creatinine in the sample. The absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically and used to calculate creatinine concentration.

Statistical Analysis

Data obtained from the study were entered into the Microsoft Excel spreadsheet (version 10) prior to descriptive analysis. The data were represented as mean \pm SEM. Paired sample Student's T-test and one-way Duncan's multiple range analysis of variance (ANOVA) were done using the IBM Corp® Statistical Package for Social Sciences, SPSS®, version 21.0.

RESULTS

Table 3 Effect of Pax Herbal Bitters on Inflammatory Marker; High Sensitive C-Reactive Protein (hs-CRP) in Male Rats Fed with High Salt Diet.

Group	Highly sensitive C-reactive protein, hs-CRP (mg/dl)
Group 1	0.30 ± 0.07 ^{ae}
Group 2	0.83 ± 0.06 ^{bc}
Group 3	0.63 ± 0.09 ^{ace}
Group 4	0.66 ± 0.05 ^{bce}

Values are represented as mean ± SEM (n=5). Values bearing different superscripts within the same column are significantly different at P < 0.05 as determined by one-way ANOVA. Group 1: Basal diet (negative control) Group 2: High salt diet (positive control) Group 3: High salt diet + lisinopril drug administration Group 4: High salt diet + low dose Pax herbal bitters administration.

The result presented in Table 4.1 shows that rats fed with the high salt diet (Group 2) had a significantly higher hs-CRP concentration compared with the negative control group (Group 1) (P < 0.05). Administration of lisinopril (Group 3) and Paxherbal bitters (Group 4) reduced hs-CRP levels compared with the positive control group (Group 2). However, the hs-CRP values in Groups 3 and 4 remained higher than those of Group 1. There was no significant difference between Groups 3 and 4 (P > 0.05).

Table 4 Effect of Low Dose Pax Herbal Bitters on Plasma Lipid Profile in Male Albino Wistar Rats Fed with High Salt Diet.

Group	Total Cholesterol (mg/dl)	HDL (mg/dl)	LDL (mg/dl)	Triglycerides (mg/dl)
Group 1	110.04 ± 9.00 ^a	38.52 ± 2.00 ^{ae^f}	57.58 ± 10.00 ^a	69.68 ± 7.00 ^a
Group 2	141.02 ± 8.00 ^{bc}	29.88 ± 2.00 ^{bc}	96.06 ± 9.00 ^{bc}	75.44 ± 5.00 ^{ac}
Group 3	149.00 ± 15.00 ^{bce}	39.84 ± 3.00 ^{ace}	94.78 ± 14.00 ^{ace}	71.98 ± 6.00 ^{ace}

Group	Total Cholesterol (mg/dl)	HDL (mg/dl)	LDL (mg/dl)	Triglycerides (mg/dl)
Group 4	109.02 ± 11.00 ^{ace}	36.30 ± 1.00 ^{ace}	58.92 ± 12.00 ^{ace}	69.04 ± 8.00 ^{ace}

Values are represented as mean ± SEM (n=5). Values with different superscripts are significantly different (P < 0.05) down the column by one-way ANOVA. Group 1: Basal diet (negative control) Group 2: High salt diet (positive control) Group 3: High salt diet + lisinopril drug administration Group 4: High salt diet + low dose Pax herbal bitters administration

Table 4 shows that total cholesterol and LDL cholesterol were significantly increased in rats fed the high salt diet (Group 2) compared with the negative control (Group 1) (P < 0.05). HDL cholesterol decreased in Group 2 relative to Group 1. Administration of lisinopril (Group 3) and Paxherbal bitters (Group 4) improved the lipid profile by increasing HDL cholesterol and reducing total cholesterol and LDL cholesterol relative to Group 2. Triglyceride levels showed no significant difference among the groups (P > 0.05).

Table 5 Hematological Profile of Various Groups after Treatments of the Rats.

Parameter	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
WBC (×10 ³ /μl)	12.68 ± 1.00	11.72 ± 1.00	7.60 ± 0.60	9.48 ± 0.80
Lymphocytes (%)	75.98 ± 4.00	77.74 ± 3.00	81.02 ± 2.00	81.42 ± 0.80
Monocytes (%)	5.28 ± 0.40	7.74 ± 0.40	6.92 ± 0.50	6.50 ± 0.60
Granulocytes (%)	18.74 ± 3.00	14.52 ± 2.00	12.06 ± 1.00	12.08 ± 0.60
RBC (×10 ⁶ /μl)	6.22 ± 0.20	6.23 ± 0.40	6.01 ± 0.20	6.90 ± 0.10
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	6.59 ± 0.30	7.28 ± 0.50	6.05 ± 0.20	7.11 ± 0.30
PCV/HCT	19.76 ± 0.70	21.85 ± 1.00	18.12 ± 0.70	21.32 ± 0.80

Parameter	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4
MCV (fl)	31.74 ± 0.70	35.12 ± 0.60	30.84 ± 0.60	30.90 ± 0.80
MCH (pg)	10.60 ± 0.20	11.68 ± 0.20	10.34 ± 0.30	10.32 ± 0.30
MCHC (g/dl)	33.32 ± 0.20	33.30 ± 0.00	33.46 ± 0.10	33.34 ± 0.04
Platelets (×10 ³ /μl)	670.80 ± 7.00	608.00 ± 2.00	633.60 ± 2.00	496.40 ± 4.00

Values are represented as mean ± SEM (n=5). Values with different superscripts are significantly different (P < 0.05) down the column by one-way ANOVA. No superscripts were assigned because the full statistical comparisons are presented in Appendix

Table 4.3 shows significant differences in WBC, monocytes, >CV, MCV, MCH and platelet counts among the treatment groups (P < 0.05), while lymphocytes, granulocytes, RBC, haemoglobin concentration and MCHC showed no significant differences (P > 0.05).

Table 6 Effect of Pax Herbal Bitters on Plasma Glucose Levels in Male Wistar Rats Fed with High Salt Diet.

Group	Plasma glucose (mg/dl)
Group 1	63.20 ± 5.00 ^a
Group 2	38.80 ± 5.00 ^{bc}
Group 3	71.00 ± 3.00 ^{ace}
Group 4	58.29 ± 5.00 ^{adf}

Values are represented as mean ± SEM (n=5). Values with different superscripts are significantly different (P < 0.05) down the column by one-way ANOVA.

The result presented in Table 6 shows that the high salt diet significantly reduced plasma glucose concentration in Group 2 compared with Group 1 (P < 0.05). Administration of lisinopril (Group 3) increased plasma glucose levels relative to Group 2. Paxherbal bitters administration (Group 4) also improved plasma glucose concentration compared with Group 2, although values remained slightly lower than those observed in Group 1.

Table 7 Effect of Pax Herbal Bitters on Plasma Kidney Function in Male Wistar Rats Fed with High Salt Diet.

Group	Plasma sodium (mmol/l)	Plasma urea (mg/dl)	Plasma creatinine (mg/dl)
Group 1	135.26 ± 1.00 ^a	33.40 ± 2.00 ^a	0.76 ± 0.05 ^a
Group 2	145.04 ± 0.30 ^{bc}	94.08 ± 1.00 ^{bc}	0.72 ± 0.08 ^{ac}
Group 3	137.36 ± 0.40 ^{ade}	82.32 ± 0.80 ^{bde}	0.64 ± 0.06 ^{ace}
Group 4	135.42 ± 1.00 ^{ade}	85.74 ± 5.00 ^{bce}	0.76 ± 0.10 ^{ace}

Values are represented as mean ± SEM (n=5). Values with different superscripts are significantly different ($P < 0.05$) down the column by one-way ANOVA.

Table 7 shows that the high salt diet significantly increased plasma sodium and urea concentrations in Group 2 compared with Group 1 ($P < 0.05$). Treatment with lisinopril (Group 3) and Paxherbal bitters (Group 4) reduced plasma sodium levels relative to Group 2. Plasma urea concentrations remained elevated in Groups 3 and 4 compared with the negative control group, although values were lower than those observed in Group 2. No significant differences were observed in plasma creatinine concentration among the groups ($P > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Discussion

Hypertension remains one of the leading causes of morbidity and mortality worldwide and is often referred to as a "silent killer" because it may remain asymptomatic during its early stages (WHO, 2013). Several studies have reported that Pax Herbal Bitters possess bioactive phytochemicals with potential therapeutic properties. Therefore, this study was designed to investigate whether low dose Pax Herbal Bitters could prevent inflammatory, haematological, biochemical and renal alterations associated with high salt diet-induced hypertension in male Wistar rats. The study also compared its effects with those of lisinopril, a standard antihypertensive drug. The results of this study show the following:

In this study it was observed that there was a significant increase in hs-CRP levels in the plasma of the rats fed with high salt diet compared to the rats fed with the basal diet. This agrees with studies carried out by Sesso et al. (2003). These scientists showed increase in inflammatory marker was observed in hypertensive rats and this was considered as part of the defense mechanism and therefore a secondary consequence to the development of hypertension. Studies by Bendich et al. (1981) showed that immune cell infiltration in the kidney may be the cause of hypertension (and not a result of it in this case). In line with this, Heijnen et al. (2004) showed that in nearly all models of salt induced hypertension, the tubulointerstitium of the kidneys of the rats were infiltrated with lymphocytes and macrophages, showing the correlation between the intensity of inflammatory cell infiltration and severe elevation in blood pressure. Also studies by De Ciuceis et al. (2005) showed another organ in which inflammation can lead to increased blood pressure is the arterial vascular wall. Vascular stiffness can either cause or be a consequence of hypertension and finally Mahmud et al. (2005) carried out cross sectional studies demonstrating significant association of markers of systemic inflammation (hs-CRP) with pulse wave velocity. This increase in the inflammatory marker (hs-CRP) was prevented in the rats given the low dose Pax herbal bitters. The reduction in hs-CRP observed following administration of Pax Herbal Bitters may be attributed to the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory phytochemicals present in the formulation, including flavonoids, alkaloids and saponins (Anionye & Onyeneke, 2016).

The present study showed that administration of a high salt diet resulted in increased plasma total cholesterol and LDL-cholesterol levels, with a concomitant reduction in HDL-cholesterol levels. These changes are indicative of dyslipidaemia and may contribute to the increased cardiovascular risk associated with hypertension. Administration of low dose Pax

Herbal Bitters improved the lipid profile by reducing total cholesterol and LDL-cholesterol concentrations while maintaining HDL-cholesterol levels close to those of the control group.

Elevated total cholesterol and LDL-cholesterol are established risk factors for cardiovascular disease, whereas HDL-cholesterol exerts a protective effect through reverse cholesterol transport (Ahmed et al., 1998; Ginsberg and Goldberg, 2001). The improvement observed following administration of Pax Herbal Bitters may be attributed to the bioactive phytochemicals present in the formulation. The findings of this study are consistent with previous reports that associate dyslipidaemia with hypertension and cardiovascular risk (Ridker et al., 2010; Mora et al., 2013).

The haematological parameters assessed in this study showed only minor variations among the experimental groups. Most parameters remained within comparable ranges, suggesting that the high salt diet did not markedly alter haematological status during the study period. Furthermore, administration of low dose Pax Herbal Bitters did not adversely affect erythrocyte, leukocyte, or platelet indices, indicating that the herbal preparation did not produce any observable adverse effects on the measured haematological indices.

Although slight changes were observed in certain indices, including haemoglobin concentration, packed cell volume, mean corpuscular volume, and platelet count, these variations did not indicate any clinically significant haematological disturbance. Overall, these findings suggest that low dose Pax Herbal Bitters does not adversely affect normal haematological function in male Wistar rats.

In this study, plasma glucose levels were significantly reduced in rats fed with a high salt diet compared to rats fed with the basal diet. Administration of lisinopril restored plasma glucose levels towards normal values than those observed in the negative control group, while administration of low dose Pax Herbal Bitters restored plasma glucose levels towards normal values. These findings suggest that the herbal bitters may help maintain glucose homeostasis under conditions of salt-induced hypertension. This observation contrasts with the findings of Yan et al. (2016), who reported an association between hypertension and hyperglycaemia in elderly Chinese subjects. The restorative effect of Pax Herbal Bitters on plasma glucose levels may be attributed to the presence of bioactive phytochemicals with glucose-regulating properties (Anionye and Onyeneke, 2016).

Plasma sodium levels were significantly increased in rats fed with a high salt diet compared with rats fed with the basal diet. Administration of lisinopril and low dose Pax Herbal Bitters prevented this increase and restored sodium levels to values comparable with

those of the negative control group. This suggests that Pax Herbal Bitters may help maintain electrolyte balance under conditions of excessive salt intake.

Plasma urea levels were significantly elevated in rats fed with a high salt diet compared with rats fed with the basal diet, indicating impairment of renal function. Although urea levels remained significantly higher than those of the negative control group following administration of lisinopril or low dose Pax Herbal Bitters, both treatments produced lower urea concentrations than the untreated high salt diet group. This suggests that the treatments may have attenuated, but did not completely prevent, the adverse effects of high salt intake on renal function.

No significant differences were observed in plasma creatinine levels among the experimental groups. This suggests that the duration of the study or the severity of salt-induced injury was insufficient to produce measurable changes in creatinine concentration. Since serum creatinine is a commonly used marker of renal function, the absence of significant changes indicates that glomerular filtration may have been largely preserved during the study period. This observation differs from findings reported by Nagah et al., who observed elevated serum creatinine levels in hypertensive subjects.

Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that low dose Pax Herbal Bitters exhibited protective effects against several biochemical and inflammatory alterations associated with high salt diet-induced hypertension in male Wistar rats. Administration of the herbal preparation significantly reduced the elevated hs-CRP levels induced by high salt feeding, suggesting an anti-inflammatory effect. The herbal bitters also improved the lipid profile by reducing total cholesterol and LDL-cholesterol concentrations while maintaining HDL-cholesterol levels.

Furthermore, low dose Pax Herbal Bitters restored plasma glucose levels towards normal values and prevented the elevation of plasma sodium concentration associated with excessive salt intake. Although plasma urea levels remained elevated, the herbal treatment appeared to attenuate the increase when compared with untreated high salt-fed rats. No significant effect was observed on plasma creatinine levels.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that low dose Pax Herbal Bitters exerted protective effects against several biochemical alterations associated with high salt diet-induced

hypertension in male Wistar rats. The herbal preparation exhibited anti-inflammatory, lipid-lowering and sodium-regulating properties without producing adverse haematological effects. Although its protective effects on renal function were only partial, the findings suggest that Pax Herbal Bitters possesses promising therapeutic potential as a complementary therapeutic agent against hypertension-associated biochemical alterations. Nevertheless, additional studies involving larger sample sizes, longer treatment durations and direct blood pressure measurements are required to further validate these findings and elucidate the underlying mechanisms of action

Limitations of the Study

This study has several limitations. First, blood pressure was not measured directly; therefore, hypertension was inferred from the established high-salt diet model and associated biochemical changes. Second, the experimental sample size was relatively small ($n = 5$ per group), which may limit statistical power. Third, although haematological analyses were performed using an automated analyser, the original analyser printouts were unavailable during thesis preparation. Consequently, interpretation was based on the laboratory values recorded during the study. Finally, the duration of treatment may not have been sufficient to detect long-term renal structural changes.

Author Contributions

Claudia Ibukunoluwa Eboigbe: Literature review, data analysis, interpretation of results, manuscript preparation and revision.

Dr John Chukwudi Anionye: Study conception and design, research supervision, methodological guidance, critical review of the manuscript, and approval of the final version.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Ethical Approval

All animal experimental procedures were conducted in accordance with the guidelines of the Canadian Council on the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals in Biomedical Research (1984) and institutional regulations governing the use of laboratory animals.

Data Availability

The data presented in this study are contained within the manuscript. Additional raw experimental records are no longer available

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